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FROM UNIVERSITY BENCH TO DIPLOMACY? UZBEKISTAN'S STRATEGIC MANEUVERING IN THE INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC LANDSCAPE

TIMUR DADABAEV and ULUGBEK AZIZOV

ABSTRACT

This paper highlights that the Uzbek government's efforts to promote collaboration in education and research serve a dual purpose of advancing academic development and branding post-dictatorial Uzbekistan. The paper argues that this approach is problematic, as issues related to the representation of Uzbek educational institutions in international academic rankings are being inaccurately treated as matters of public policy and diplomacy. The paper demonstrates that educational collaborations constitute subsystems that impact a country's image but cannot be significantly influenced by public policy and diplomacy alone. It is, therefore, important for public policy officials to recognize and understand education as a subsystem operating independently from inter-state relations, and to acquire the necessary skills to navigate it effectively.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, education, Central Asia, discourse; functional differentiation; a global society in science.

INTRODUCTION

With his election in 2016, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan set the task of promoting the international image of Uzbekistan in various sectors such as economy, education, research, welfare, and other¹. Such a policy of international outreach has had a tremendous impact on the country's engagement in the international scientific landscape. The government of Uzbekistan stressed the importance of the inclusion of the

country's educational institutions into international academic ranking systems not only as a matter of educational/scientific development but also as a matter of changing the international image of the country in terms of diplomacy and international public policy.

There are various views on the motivations of governments in encouraging educational institutions to expand their international outreach. Several academic studies analyze government motivations for international educational cooperation and inclusion in academic rankings. Gita Steiner-Khamsi and colleagues² examine the motivations behind international educational borrowing and lending, arguing that countries engage in such practices to promote their own interests and achieve specific policy goals. Wagemaker et.al³ explore the factors related to why governments participate in international student assessments such as PISA, finding that they do so to benchmark their own educational systems, identify areas for improvement, and compare their performance to other countries. Furthermore, Hazelkorn et.al⁴ analyze the motivations behind countries' participation in global university rankings, arguing that they do so to attract international students and faculty, improve their research performance, and enhance their global reputation. Alternatively, Ka-Ho Mok and Kar Ming Yu⁵ explore the motivations behind the internationalization of higher education in East Asia, arguing that governments engage in such practices to promote economic development, enhance their global competitiveness, and prepare their students for the challenges of the future.

Regarding the motivations of governments to participate in academic rankings, Marginson⁶ highlights the implications of global university rankings for the field of education and argues that these are becoming increasingly important for governments, universities, and students. Marope, Wells and Hazelkorn⁷ examine the uses and misuses of academic rankings in higher education, arguing that while these can be useful for benchmarking and improving quality, these can also be misused for purposes of competition, prestige, and commercial gain. Overall, these studies suggest that global rankings are becoming increasingly important

in the field of education and have significant implications for governments, universities, and students. They also highlight the politics surrounding rankings and the potential for their misuse, emphasizing the need for critical analysis and careful consideration of their impact.

These studies provide an important assessment of the role and place attributed to educational rankings by developing countries to encourage their universities to participate in the global educational exchange. However, when considering the case of Uzbekistan, the factors primarily important for such proactive educational internationalization are not clearly defined, while there is a general assumption that internationalization for educational institutions automatically brings positive outcomes. In the light of this problem, this paper attempts to uncover the reasons primarily related to the active policies in respect to international outreach in higher education undertaken by the government of Uzbekistan and Uzbek educational institutions in recent years.

What factors can account for Uzbekistan's government's keen interest in engaging with the international scientific community? What are the practical and theoretical challenges of Uzbekistan's academic and educational outreach to foreign partners for its government and academic institutions?

By answering a set of questions, this paper sheds light on the motivations of the Uzbek government in promoting educational and academic collaborations among national institutions. Specifically, the paper emphasizes that while the government's goal is to achieve higher standards of education and training for economic development, it also considers participation in such collaboration schemes as an essential element in enhancing the international prestige of Uzbekistan. The government believes that Uzbekistan's recognition is crucial in attracting foreign investments. Therefore, the purpose of the Uzbek government's policy of promoting collaboration in education and research goes beyond the goals of academic development and includes the branding of post-dictatorial Uzbekistan.

The paper also argues that issues regarding the representation of

Uzbek educational institutions in international academic rankings are incorrectly interpreted as a subject of public policy and diplomacy. While the government's intentions are well-intentioned, it is not possible to easily correct or improve educational and academic performances through a single policy or investment initiative. Educational collaborations form subsystems that affect the image of countries, but they cannot be changed voluntarily over a short period and through the channels of public diplomacy alone. Global rankings, such as the Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings (QS), exemplify these sub-systemic functions, which include metrics such as "Academic Reputation (AR)," "Employer Reputation (ER)," "Faculty/Student Ratio (F/SR)," "Citation Per Faculty (CPF)," "International Faculty Ratio/International Student Ratio." It is vital for Uzbekistan's government officials and university administrators to understand the educational/academic subsystem's logic to properly define their educational policy goals in the long term.

This article develops its argument in the following three sections. The first section outlines the conceptual framework for understanding the governmentally enforced internationalization of educational institutions. While doing so, we will demonstrate how educational/academic sectors operate, aside from politics, based on their logic of constituting societies at a global level. The second section interprets Uzbekistan's international politics from this scientific perspective, focusing on how the country's foreign policy choice is being guided by the functional differentiation logic within the science. The third section concludes with a discussion of the implications of our analysis for understanding the motivations of the Uzbek government in promoting educational and academic collaboration.

FUNCTIONAL DIFFERENTIATION: THEORIZING UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE SCIENCE

The interpretation of Uzbekistan's international politics from the science perspective entails scrutiny of the science as a functionally self-organized

international entity, in contrast to the notions of geopolitics, balancing/ bandwagoning, regime security, inclusion/exclusion context, and strategies and discourses of world/regional powers in Central Asia which often dominate coverage of regional states representation at the global level. Therefore, this section focuses on the interpretation of the science, its global (self-referential) institutions such as QS, and how Uzbekistan and its public engagement with this institution shape its global identity.

Recent studies on functional differentiation in IR (Albert; Buzan and Albert; Albert and Hilkermeier; Albert, Kessler, and Stetter; Cerny; Helmig and Kessler, Azizov)⁸ have plausibly argued that the modern world consists of functionally differentiated subsystems: for example, a subsystem in science (i.e., the science), a subsystem in politics (i.e., the politics), and others. In this regard, this paper refers to the academic and educational sector when using "the science" as the term. Each subsystem organizes societies according to its own (transnational) tasks that state- and non-state actors fulfill at a global level. Thus, under this functional differentiation logic, international politics is not only characterized by the cross-border interactions of state- and non-state actors from the domination/opposition perspective but also by the knowledge production functional logic (in the science, for example).

Functional differentiation regards the science as the autonomous social subsystem, implying that each subsystem operates based on its own functional logic; thus, neither the science nor the politics could impose their own perspective on each other. For example, the functional logic of the science is characterized by its code of true/false, while the politics is driven by the code of domination/opposition. In the modern world, societies are organized by fulfilling transnational tasks based on true/false as well as domination/opposition perspectives. As such, the politics can only tackle its own problems and can generate its own intersubjective rules and meanings, which cannot be binding in the science and vice versa⁹.

Consequently, the science should be approached separately from the politics. Societies that are organized around the function of producing knowledge (based on the verification of a new theory that falsifies other

theories) have little if anything to do with the notions of struggling for domination (either in domestic or foreign politics) or power. This paper does recognize that even academic rankings are produced in Western institutions and represent the way to empower certain countries and control the narration of the knowledge generation and the images projected by non-Western states and Central Asia in particular (see Cooley and Snyder, Dadabaev, and Heathershaw)¹⁰. This point is also similar to those already mentioned by others such as Fehl and Freistein¹¹ pointing at how international organizations rank their members into unequal social positions, stating that international organizations “define what social positions exist, to what socially valued rewards these positions are entitled or not entitled, and who gets access to these positions”.¹² However, as far as the operationalization of these rankings is concerned, the academic community is primarily concerned with the problem of verifying or falsifying certain approaches, and recognizing the value of certain theories/methodologies/notions, which are communicated through publications, citations, attracted research funds, academic infrastructure and the number of students among many other criteria (Ziemann; Gren and Zierhofer; Luhmann; Moeller)¹³.

The division of the modern world into subsystems took place gradually due to the process of globalization and specialization of each subsystem (based on its functional code). Modern societies are ordered less and less by a single center (i.e., the politics); rather, they are organized more and more around global functions they are engaged within different self-referential subsystems. For example, the science’s self-referential logic is conditioned by “[o]perations of the same kind have to be capable of connecting to each other so that a network of operations arises”.¹⁴ This implies that at an operational level, the science refers to its own operation (verification/falsification communicated via publications) to be capable of producing social connectivity for societies globally.

As such, the science is “composed of elements (events [e.g., falsification/verification communicated via publications]) that refer to themselves by including their connection with other elements of the same

process".¹⁵ "Therefore, communications (publications) are determined by nothing else but communications (other publications)".¹⁶ Hence, communication in science is not characterized by the "physical quality of its signs nor in the conscious states of its speakers and listeners, readers, and writers", but by any possibility of "constituting self-generated forms".¹⁷ Uzbekistan, like other actors, observes how communications communicate self-referentially according to the science's code, program, operation, and medium; the country is also observed by the science concerning how it (and its public) participates in the science's operation at a global level.

The science's metrics interpret cross-border interactions taking place in-between state and non-state actors, universities, scholars, experts, students, and others who are engaged in producing knowledge at a global level. For example, the metrics collect "the expert opinions of over 94,000 individuals in the higher education space regarding teaching and research quality at the world's universities" (AR).¹⁸ Research quality is in turn determined by self-referentiality, implying that an assumption developed in a published article refers to nothing else but the assumptions discussed in previously published articles. Thus, CPF takes into consideration cross-border systemic communications in the form of "citations received by all papers produced by an institution across a five-year period by the number of faculty members at that institution." Using data from Elsevier's Scopus database, the "QS assessed 74 million citations from 13.5 million papers" in 2019 across the globe.¹⁹ And, it continues to do so annually as the science continues securing social connectivity and constructing functional spatiality among societies.

Following this self-referential communicative logic, the science produces and reproduces states' conceptual boundaries, which are less and less about distinctions between territorial units and regional constituencies (e.g., Central Asia and its external Others) and more and more about a functional division between the science and other subsystems.²⁰ Within the scientific borderland, the QS itself constitutes who the Self is and whom the Others are based on actors' participation in the subsystem's operation. Thus, the science consists of a set of observable

communicative events (publications) as well as of a set of perceptions (norms, identities) of actors about these events.²¹ Identity construction within the science hence “relies neither on the need for the denial and suppression of the Other (e.g., Uzbekistan and its excluded Other) nor on the conscious selection of behavior based on a particular norm (e.g., Turkic-speaking nation)”.²² Such identity constitution in science is determined functionally in terms of inclusion (a global society in the science) and its exclusion (other functionally determined global societies). In this regard, the construction of Uzbekistan’s international image occurs in terms of this global scientific functional borderland rather than Uzbekistan’s branding policy or diplomacy. The government of Uzbekistan however, displays signs of lacking the understanding of this essence of educational rankings as it pursues a very active policy of nation-branding through public diplomacy acts.

THE SCIENCE, THE QS, AND UZBEKISTAN’S ENGAGEMENT WITH THE SUBSYSTEM

To exemplify a few cases, MOFA of Uzbekistan has reported that for instance, the ambassador of Uzbekistan to the Benelux countries, Dilyor Khakimov, met with the representatives of the Dutch company Elsevier on January 28, 2020, to discuss the prospects of the Ilm-Fan [Science] 2020 project launched in March 2018 together with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education to provide all higher education institutions and research institutes with the access to the most cited scientific journals and books, the largest scientific and analytical platform, Scopus, and facilitating more than 230 training workshops.²³ It was also stated that such support from Elsevier resulted in two universities of Uzbekistan – Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers and Tashkent University of Information Technologies – having been included in QS World University Rankings rating for the quality of teaching certain subjects.

Another step directed to meet the Presidential agenda of promoting

the image of Uzbekistan abroad has been setting up new educational institutions with foreign partners. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2019, released an announcement about a plan to open the University of Technology of Malaysia (UTM) in the city of Khorezm, Uzbekistan.²⁴ The earlier news released on June 17, 2017, via the official webpage of the Embassy of Uzbekistan in Germany also announced the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding with Leicester University, England, to establish the Leicester School of International Studies at the University of World Economy and Diplomacy under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan.²⁵ Here, it is important to note that the (functional) images of Malaysia and the United Kingdom are perceived through the science that it produces for Uzbekistan. UTM is ranked 228th by the QS World University Rankings and 47th by the QS Asian University Rankings²⁶, Leicester University “is one of leading public research universities of UK and within 1% of top universities according to Times HE ranking, 2% – according to the QS World University Rankings and 25th in the list of the top university of UK”.²⁷

In a similar manner, the Foreign Ministry of Uzbekistan annotated the meeting of the Uzbek ambassador to Italy Otabek Akbarov with the representatives of the University of Pisa (ranked 389th in the QS ranking of 2020) to discuss the possibility of establishing a branch of the university in Tashkent.²⁸ On a separate, but conceptually related, occasion, Minister of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan Abdulaziz Kamilov met with a member of the Board of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Russia, Rector of Moscow State Institute of International Relations (MGIMO) Anatoly Torkunov on December 9, 2019. Mr. Torkunov arrived in Uzbekistan to attend the official opening ceremony of MGIMO in Tashkent²⁹, the image of which is supported by QS (ranked 355th in 2019).

Other programs and engagements carefully considered by the Uzbek government included the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), The Bologna Process (a series of reforms that aim to promote student mobility and quality assurance in higher education), the UNESCO World Conference on Education for Sustainable Development as well as

the Global Education Monitoring Report (annual report produced by UNESCO that tracks progress towards the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal of providing inclusive and equitable quality education for all).

On October 25, 2019, the central TV channel of Uzbekistan “Axborot 24” showed a film³⁰, analyzing the sector of higher education in the country. The film criticized that none of the 114 public universities functioning in Uzbekistan have been ranked globally so far by the QS among the top 1000 world universities. Comparing other institutions in close geographic proximity to Uzbekistan, the film mentioned Russia’s Lomonosov Moscow State University (ranked 90th by the QS in 2019), Kazakhstan’s Al-Farabi National University (ranked 220th by the QS in 2019), and Gumilyov Eurasian National University in Kazakhstan (ranked 394th by the QS in 2019)³¹.

The demonstration of the film came right after Uzbekistan President Shavkat Mirziyoyev approved the Development Concept of the Higher Education System of Uzbekistan by 2030.³² The Development Concept points at the necessity for Uzbekistan public universities to engage with the QS, and by doing so, to achieve the goal of being ranked among the top 1000 world universities by 2030. Earlier, ex-Minister of Higher Education of Uzbekistan Inom Majidov and QS Regional Director Zoya Zaitseva signed a strategic agreement to support Uzbekistan universities to join World University Rankings (WUR) within the framework of the Ilm-fan [Science] 2020 program. According to this agreement, the QS Intelligence Unit is now assisting in clarifying the methodology of joining WUR and justifying the strengths and weaknesses of Uzbekistan public universities on the QS’s key indicators.³³ In recent years, the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers has been ranked 323th in QS University Regional Rankings: Emerging Europe and Central Asia. The Ministry of Higher Education of Uzbekistan hurried to highlight this exemplary role model which should be followed by other public universities in the country.³⁴

As is illustrated above, Uzbekistan’s public and educational policy

which encourages international tie-ups is heavily informed by the international standing of various countries in prestigious academic rankings. For instance, for the Uzbek government, the image of the United States as projected in various rankings is positive (i.e., the successful Self) as the QS annually ranks the United States universities among the top best world universities. According to the QS World University Rankings 2020³⁵, out of the top 10 universities ranked by the QS, 5 are from the United States. Other countries such as the United Kingdom, Germany, France, Japan, Russia, South Korea, etc. are listed within the top 1000 world universities.³⁶ Since the Uzbek government promotes the policy according to which its universities need to be listed among these 1000 world universities by 2030, the country tries to imitate the functional successes that the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, Japan, Russia, and South Korea have achieved in the science so far. Uzbekistan develops a sense of these countries through how the scientific rankings construct their images (within the top 1000 world universities). In such a structure, the essence of the collaboration or the value of the product produced by the tie-ups with these top-tier universities becomes of secondary importance for the government as it sees collaboration as a part of the branding strategy of the country.

Consequently, Uzbekistan President Mirziyoyev's decree³⁷ on launching the US Webster University in Tashkent implies that the opening of this university in Tashkent is a way of becoming closer to the success of the United States in science, and learning how the country could achieve the goal of being ranked amongst the top 1000 world universities by 2030. In this regard, the decree reasons that the attraction of modern pedagogical technologies (from the United States) will help to train cadres in Uzbekistan based on international educational standards. In this functional reasoning context, there is a possibility for Uzbekistan and the United States (as well as for others that are listed within the top QS 1000 world universities) to coexist within the common functional space in the science without attaching the images of hegemon or balancer in the Central Asian borderland.

Generally, Uzbekistan's interaction with the QS is characterized by its willingness to be recognized in a global society in the science. In this scientific subsystem, the representation of Uzbekistan is defined by the functional performance logic of individual researchers with little direct input and impact of the government in this functional differentiation process. The images of the United States and/or Russia or other countries which do well in the academic rankings are transmitted to Uzbekistan via the operation logic of the science. QS's AR is a metric, through which expert reflections of over 94,000 individuals from 140 countries travel across national borders each year, projecting the image and the role of the particular country in the international standing of this scientific subsystem.

At the same time, although the government of Uzbekistan operates with the vision that representation in global educational rankings is part of the country's foreign policy and relates to the images projected on the country in the field of international relations, there are little, if any operational tools the government possesses or can apply to change country's standing in a short-term. There is a need for a deeper understanding among policy officials that the academic subsystem of interactions has its own functional logic, which is not necessarily compatible with the notions often cited in the field of diplomacy or international politics.

Consequently, Uzbekistan's interactions with the United States and/or Russia within the realm of the science are not characterized by the logic of domination/opposition, which involves strategies and discourses of world/regional powers that shape perceptions of influence in Uzbekistan and the region. Instead, these interactions are conditioned by the production of knowledge that is assessed and perceived through the functional logic of the metrics such as AR and CPF. Therefore, regardless of how the discourse of the five Stans assesses the United States and/or Russia as geopolitically dangerous Others in Central Asia, these assessments and perceptions have no bearing on the images of the United States or Russia that the QS constructs in its functional self-referential context for the Uzbek government.

PUBLISHING AS A SYSTEMIC SELF-REFERENTIAL EVENT

In a similar manner to the issue of improving international collaboration, the issue of increasing international visibility and academic representation of scholars from Uzbekistan is also considered to be an important pillar of governmental policy and diplomacy. For instance, on December 6, 2019, the Ministry of Higher Education of Uzbekistan jointly with the Elsevier Company (Netherlands) hosted a ceremony, “the Scopus Award – 2019”. The ceremony was attended by Deputy Prime Minister of Uzbekistan Aziz Abdukhakimov, then Deputy Minister of Higher Education of Uzbekistan Uzoqboy Begimqulov, the representative of ranking agencies such as QS, Times Higher Education, etc. During the ceremony, several Uzbek scholars were announced as awardees.³⁸ Uzbekistan hosted the same ceremony in 2018 and plans to conduct it in years to come with more and more Uzbek scholars to be nominated for this award.

The Scopus Award is a process of ranking individuals based on the logic of self-referentiality in the science. This ranking is characterized by assessing the number of publications in journals (indexed in Scopus) and of citations that these publications have by other publications. Scopus's ranking is not a political act (no single center could decide on this ranking); but, it obeys the self-referential logic of the science. Previous publications cause new publications, which cause future publications to be written. Thus, Uzbek scholars' participation through their publications in the science is a systemic self-referential decision. As such, these Uzbek scholars are connected with other international scholars through academic debates communicated via publications. This systemic communicative connectivity among scholars takes place within Scopus; that is, Elsevier's citation database, which covers more than 23,000 titles from more than 5,000 international publishers. Scopus is also used by the QS to rank universities in World University Rankings each year. Scopus Awards initially were awarded in 2004. Since that time, Scopus Awards have been granted to scholars from Latin America, Asia (including Uzbekistan), Europe, and Russia.³⁹

Although the events associated with the Scopus Awards are considered to boost the public image of a country and serve as another marker for international recognition, there is a misinterpretation of these awards among the Uzbek policymakers as signifying the national (as opposed to individual scholars) achievement of a particular country, which they do not. In this regard the following needs to be reasserted. Scopus does not draw conceptual boundaries based on factors such as nationality, ethnicity, or political views. It only recognizes the value of what has been published based on the citation code, implying that Uzbek and other scholars are motivated by the desire to verify or falsify their ideas at the operational level of science. Consequently, citations are indexed and assessed through the h-index and i10-indexes which eventually define whose ideas are appreciated the most among fellow academics. In the same way, Google Scholar identifies scholars, not their countries of origin, using the h-index and i10-index. The choice of which articles to cite does not follow the political will of a government, but the logic of self-referentiality within the subsystem. Thus, within the science, whether one belongs to the United States, Russia, or Uzbekistan, scholars remain socially connected individually at a systemic level once their papers/works are accepted for publication/presentation etc., and this cross-border connectivity is assessed and observed only through the categories similar to h-index and i10-indexes (however artificial they are), and not through the politics (implying public diplomacy or national influence/power).

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has examined Uzbekistan's participation in educational and academic rankings from a functional perspective, arguing that in the era of functional differentiation, "the politics" alone cannot fully explain all cross-border societal interactions. This paper also communicates the message that academic/educational collaborations constitute subsystems that impact a country's image but cannot be significantly influenced by public policy and diplomacy alone. It is therefore important for public

policy officials to recognize and understand education as a subsystem operating independently from inter-state relations, and to acquire the necessary skills to navigate it effectively.

The paper has highlighted that contemporary interactions in various sectors, including science, are made up of functionally determined subsystems that are characterized by their differentiated nature and driven by their respective codes. As a result, the construction of Uzbekistan's international representation in science is distinct from its representation in the field of diplomacy and international relations, that is, politics. Each subsystem produces and reproduces different meanings and images for Uzbekistan's international politics. To assume that the issue of representation in academic/educational reputation rankings is the same as the representation of the country in the diplomatic field, and to generalize these meanings and images, leads to a failure in understanding the differentiated cross-border practices in international public policy.

In conclusion, this paper has demonstrated the importance of analyzing cross-border societal interactions from a functional perspective and taking into account the differentiated nature of subsystems. It aims to contribute to the understanding of how Uzbekistan's participation in educational and academic rankings at a systemic level fits into the larger context of its international politics and diplomacy and provides a basis for further research in this area.

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